

August CCI----WT (C57B/6, Hv1 KO), Male---CCI by Junyun He
 C57BL/6 male mice from Jackson

Groups	Cage #	mouse ID	Tail bars	Body weight (g)	DOB	date of CCI	
Sham/WT (n=2)	Cage 1	J1	1	25.8	10 w	8/21/18	
	Cage 6	J26	1	27.3	10 w	8/21/18	
Sham/WT (n=8)	old-1	1			12 mon old	7/23/2019arrive	
		2					
		3					
		4					
	old-2	5					
		6					
		7					
		8					

Sham/Hv1 KO (n=10)	Hv1-41	6677	2	25.6		8/21/18
		6678	no	24.6		8/21/18
	Hv1-42	6679	1	28.4	6/4/18	8/22/18
		6680	2	28.9		8/22/18
	isolated in MSTF	6681	3	28.3		8/22/18
from breeders	old Hv1-8	792			8/4/18	
from breeders	old Hv1-9	793			8/4/18	
	Hv1-84	1			1/28/19	
		2			1/28/19	
		3			1/28/19	

TBI/WT (n=8)	Cage 3	J11	1	31.8	10 w	8/21/18
		J12	2	27.4		8/21/18
		J14	4	27.6		8/21/18
	Cage 4	J16	1	27.6	10 w	8/21/18
		J17	2	27.4		8/21/18
		J18	3	30.7		8/21/18
		J19	4	28.7		8/22/18
		J20	no		27.9	
TBI/Hv1 KO (n=7)	Hv1-34	6645	1	25.6	5/17/18	8/21/18
		6646	2	25.5		8/21/18
		6648	3	26.3		8/21/18
		6650	4	26.8		8/21/18
		6652	no			
	Hv1-36	6660	2	26.8		8/22/18
6663		3	27.5		8/22/18	
6666		4	27.3		8/22/18	

dead

35

Sham/WT, N=10
Sham/Hv1 KO, N=10
TBI/WT, n=8
TBI/Hv1 KO, n=7

young adult mice as sham control for Flow Cytometry

10	DOB
Cage 1 (C57B/L6 mice)	April, 2019
Hv1-104 (170,171,172,173)	6/10/19

test	date of behavior	PID
open field	7/29/19	342
CatWalk	7/30/19	343
Y-Maze	7/31/19	344
NOR	7/31/19~8/2/2019	344-346
Forced Swim	8/3/19	347
Social Interaction	8/4/19	348
Nest Building	8/8/19	352
Sucrose Preference	8/9/19	353
Hot Plate	8/19/19	363
Grip Strength	8/29/19	373

7/29/2019 Open Field----10min Run Time, performed by Yun Li (PID 342)

Group	Cage #	Mice ID	Tail Bars	
Sham/WT (n=10)	Cage 1	J1	no	
	Cage 6	J26	no	
	old WT-1		1	1
			2	2
			3	3
			4	4
			5	no
	old WT-2		6	1
			7	2
			8	no

Mean
SEM

Sham/Hv1 KO (n=10)	Hv1-41	6677	1
		6678	no
	Hv1-42	6679	1
		6680	2
		6681	no
	old Hv1-8	792	no
	old Hv1-9	793	no
	Hv1-84	1	1
		2	2
		3	no

Mean
SEM

TBI/WT (n=8)	Cage 3	J11	1
		J12	2
		J14	4
	Cage 4	J16	1
		J17	2
		J18	3
		J19	4
		J20	no

Mean
SEM

TBI/Hv1 KO (n=7)	Hv1-34	6645	1
		6646	2
		6648	3
		6650	4
	Hv1-36	6660	1
		6663	2

		6666	no
--	--	-------------	-----------

Mean
SEM

Total Distance Travelle

Sham-WT

Mean 34.16
SEM 2.09

Mean Speed

Sham-WT

Mean 0.06
SEM 0.00

Time Mobile

Sham-WT

Mean 462.85
SEM 9.69

Time Immobile

Sham-WT

Mean 137.15
SEM 9.69

Percentage of Time Spent on In

Sham-WT

Mean 31.13
SEM 3.22

Duration	Distance	Mean speed	Time mobile
600.0	37.133	0.062	437.2
600.0	42.698	0.071	489.7
600.0	40.283	0.067	498.5
600.0	33.029	0.055	458.5
600.0	34.330	0.057	447.5
600.0	31.476	0.052	483.7
600.0	27.082	0.045	443.1
600.0	31.405	0.052	459.6
600.0	22.117	0.037	407.4
600.0	42.052	0.070	503.3
600.00	34.16	0.06	462.85
0.00	2.09	0.00	9.69
600.0	23.627	0.039	327.3
600.0	19.241	0.032	282.1
600.0	23.986	0.040	415.3
600.0	34.972	0.058	493.4
600.0	17.443	0.029	376.9
600.0	43.952	0.073	518.5
600.0	33.151	0.055	456.8
600.0	33.856	0.056	490.2
600.0	38.367	0.064	456.5
600.0	31.596	0.053	442.8
600.00	30.02	0.05	425.98
0.00	2.72	0.00	24.12
600.0	23.895	0.040	363.5
600.0	40.715	0.068	502.2
600.0	46.406	0.077	542.6
600.0	19.091	0.032	305.1
600.0	30.726	0.051	436.3
600.0	33.828	0.056	435.3
600.0	48.641	0.081	542.5
600.0	33.595	0.056	415.9
600.00	34.61	0.06	442.93
0.00	3.65	0.01	29.73
600.0	39.593	0.066	448.0
600.0	38.385	0.064	458.1
600.0	57.599	0.096	548.6
600.0	36.929	0.062	464.1
600.0	30.107	0.050	395.7
600.0	32.873	0.055	452.9

600.0	53.785	0.090	506.9
600.00	41.32	0.07	467.76
0.00	3.93	0.01	18.24

ed

Sham-Hv1 KO	TBI-WT	TBI-Hv1 KO
30.02	34.61	41.32
2.72	3.65	3.93

Sham-Hv1 KO	TBI-WT	TBI-Hv1 KO
0.05	0.06	0.07
0.00	0.01	0.01

Sham-Hv1 KO	TBI-WT	TBI-Hv1 KO
425.98	442.93	467.76
24.12	29.73	18.24

Sham-Hv1 KO	TBI-WT	TBI-Hv1 KO
174.02	157.08	132.21
24.12	29.73	18.25

side Zone

Sham-Hv1 KO	TBI-WT	TBI-Hv1 KO
31.67	35.05	38.70
2.96	4.16	2.98

Time immobile	Outside Zone : time	Outside Zone : distance
162.8	425.8	20.602
110.3	281.1	13.290
101.5	458.7	26.588
141.5	460.1	22.968
152.5	493.0	24.306
116.3	437.4	20.580
156.9	407.2	16.581
140.4	394.3	17.157
192.6	348.9	12.555
96.7	425.5	22.812
137.15	413.20	19.74
9.69	19.30	1.49
272.7	380.4	11.955
317.9	553.6	15.548
184.7	391.8	11.590
106.6	395.7	18.134
223.1	430.5	8.008
81.5	347.6	20.617
143.2	416.0	18.358
109.8	368.4	14.671
143.5	394.5	17.843
157.2	421.1	17.478
174.02	409.96	15.42
24.12	17.79	1.23
236.5	392.3	13.042
97.8	392.1	25.261
57.4	344.6	23.932
294.9	488.9	10.491
163.7	369.9	16.169
164.7	268.2	13.205
57.5	383.3	22.136
184.1	478.3	24.755
157.08	389.70	18.62
29.73	24.98	2.13
152.0	441.1	24.723
141.8	317.5	19.348
51.4	386.5	28.546
135.9	392.7	20.455
204.3	386.1	15.378
147.1	307.7	13.394

93.0
132.21
18.25

343.2
367.83
17.88

22.831
20.67
1.99

al Distance

ean Speed

ne Mobile

Time Immobile

ne on Inside Zone

Inside Zone : time	Inside Zone : distance	of time spent on Inside Zo
174.2	16.531	29.03
318.9	29.408	53.15
141.3	13.695	23.55
139.9	10.061	23.32
107.0	10.024	17.83
162.6	10.896	27.10
192.8	10.501	32.13
205.7	14.248	34.28
251.1	9.562	41.85
174.5	19.240	29.08
186.80	14.42	31.13
19.30	1.95	3.22
219.6	11.671	36.60
46.4	3.693	7.73
208.2	12.396	34.70
204.3	16.837	34.05
169.5	9.435	28.25
252.4	23.335	42.07
184.0	14.793	30.67
231.6	19.185	38.60
205.5	20.524	34.25
178.9	14.119	29.82
190.04	14.60	31.67
17.79	1.82	2.96
207.7	10.853	34.62
207.9	15.454	34.65
255.4	22.474	42.57
111.1	8.600	18.52
230.1	14.557	38.35
331.8	20.623	55.30
216.7	26.505	36.12
121.7	8.840	20.28
210.30	15.99	35.05
24.98	2.35	4.16
158.9	14.871	26.48
282.5	19.037	47.08
213.5	29.053	35.58
207.3	16.474	34.55
213.9	14.729	35.65
292.3	19.478	48.72

256.8	30.955	42.80
232.17	20.66	38.70
17.88	2.52	2.98

7/31/2019 Y-Maze Test, 6 min Run Time (PID 344)

Group	Cage #	Mice ID	Tail Bar	ABACBA	#total arms				
					alteration	entered			
Sham/WT (n=10)	Cage 1	J1	1	ABCABCACBACBACBACBCBACBABCBCBACBABCBCBACBACB	33	46	75.0%		
		Cage 6	J26	1	ABACBCABACBABCBCACBACBACBABCBC	20	31	69.0%	
		old WT-1	1	1	ACBCACBCABCBCACBCBABCACBACBACBA	20	30	71.4%	
			2	2	CABCBCBACBCABCACBCACAC	13	25	56.5%	
			3	3	BABCBCABCBCABCBCACABCBCACBCABCACBAC	22	39	59.5%	
			4	4	CBACABCACABCACABCBCACBACB	17	27	68.0%	
			5	no	CACBCACABABCBCACBCACBACBACBACBA	14	26	58.3%	
		old WT-2	6	1	ACABCACBCABCACBABCBCABC	11	22	55.0%	
			7	2	ACBACBACBACBCACBCBACB	15	21	78.9%	
			8	no	BACABCACBABCACBABCBCABCBCB	19	29	70.4%	
Sham/Hv1 KO (n=10)	Hv1-41	6677	1	BACBABACBABCACBACBAC	14	20	77.8%	X	
		6678	no	BACACBACBCABCBCABCACBA	15	25	65.2%	SD	
	Hv1-42	6679	1	CBABCACBABCABCABCABC	13	22	65.0%	SE	
		6680	2	BCABCBCBABCABCABCBCBA	16	24	72.7%		
		6681	no	BCACABCBCABCBCABCABC	10	21	52.6%		
	old Hv1-8	792	no	CACBCBCABCABCABCABCABCBCABC	18	28	69.2%		
	old Hv1-9	793	no	BCABCBCABCABCABCBCBABCBA	16	24	72.7%		
	Hv1-84	1	1	BABCBCACABCBA	6	14	50.0%		
		2	2	BCACBCABCACBABCACBABCBCBABA	16	27	64.0%		
			3	no	ABCACACBA	5	10	62.5%	
TBI/WT (n=8)	Cage 3	J11	1	BCBACBCBCACABCACABCBCACBCACBACABAC	16	35	48.5%		
		J12	2	ABACBACABCABCABCABCACBACBABC	17	28	65.4%		
		J14	4	CACBCBABCABCABCACABCBCABCABCBCBA	17	35	51.5%		
	Cage 4	J16	1	CBABCABCABCABCABCABCABC	15	24	68.2%		
		J17	2	BCABCACABCABCABCABC	13	20	72.2%		
		J18	3	CBACABCACABCABCABCACBABCACBCACBABCBCACBABCABC	32	47	71.1%		
		J19	4	CABCABCABCABCBCABCABCABCACABCABC	24	36	70.6%		
		J20	no	ACBACBACBCABCABCABCABCABCBC	21	30	75.0%		
TBI/Hv1 KO (n=8)	Hv1-34	6645	1	BACABABACBACABCBCBABA	10	20	55.6%		
		6646	2	ACBCACBCABCABCABCABCABCBA	19	27	76.0%		
		6648	3	ABCABCABCABCABCABCABCABCABC	27	36	79.4%		
		6650	4	CBABCABCABCABCABCABCABCBCACBCABCBCBA	23	37	65.7%		
	Hv1-36	6660	1	BACABCABCABCABCABC	14	20	77.8%		
		6663	2	BCACBCACBABCACABCABCBCABCBCBABA	16	32	53.3%		
		6666	no	ABCABCABCABCABCABCABC	19	23	90.5%		

alteration%

Sham/WT	TBI/WT	Sham/Hv1 ko	TBI/Hv1 ko
75.0%	48.5%	77.8%	55.6%
69.0%	65.4%	65.2%	76.0%
71.4%	51.5%	65.0%	79.4%
56.5%	68.2%	72.7%	65.7%
59.5%	72.2%	52.6%	77.8%
68.0%	71.1%	69.2%	53.3%
58.3%	70.6%	72.7%	90.5%
55.0%	75.0%	50.0%	
78.9%		64.0%	
70.4%		62.5%	
66.2%	65.3%	65.2%	71.2%
8.3%	9.9%	8.7%	13.5%
2.6%	3.5%	2.8%	5.1%

total #

Sham/WT	TBI/WT	Sham/Hv1 ko	TBI/Hv1 ko
46	35	20	20
31	28	25	27
30	35	22	36
25	24	24	37
39	20	21	20
27	47	28	32
26	36	24	23
22	30	14	
21		27	
29		10	
29.6	31.9	21.5	27.9
7.7	8.3	5.7	7.2
2.4	2.9	1.8	2.7

8/3/2019 Forced Swim (6 min), PID 347

Group	Cage #	Mice ID	Tail Bar	Time Immobile	
Sham/WT (n=10)	Cage 1	J1	1	112	
	Cage 6	J26	1	74	
	old WT-1		1	1	80
			2	2	138
			3	3	75
			4	4	133
	old WT-2		5	no	65
			6	1	112
			7	2	107
			8	no	148
			Mean	104.40	
			SEM	9.37	

Sham/Hv1 KO (n=10)	Hv1-41	6677	1	92	
		6678	no	119	
	Hv1-42	6679	1	63	
		6680	2	133	
		6681	no	129	
	old Hv1-8	792	no	137	
	old Hv1-9	793	no	117	
	Hv1-84	1	1	140	
		2	2	105	
		3	no	89	
				Mean	112.40
				SEM	7.88

TBI/WT (n=8)	Cage 3	J11	1	109
		J12	2	128
		J14	4	116
	Cage 4	J16	1	107
		J17	2	142
		J18	3	151
		J19	4	162
		J20	no	186
			SEM	9.87

TBI/Hv1 KO (n=8)	Hv1-34	6645	1	104
		6646	2	131
		6648	3	151
		6650	4	159
	Hv1-36	6660	1	157

		6663	2	149
		6666	no	122

Mean 139.00
SEM 7.79

	Sham-WT	Sham-Hv1 KO
Mean	104.40	112.40
SEM	9.37	7.88

TBI-WT	TBI-Hv1 KO
137.63	139.00
9.87	7.79

wim

7/31~8/2/19 Novel Object Recognition (PID 344-346)

d2 NOR

d3 NOR

Group	Cage #	Mice ID	Tail Bar	Time with Left Object		Time with Right Object		Time with Left Object		Time with Right Object		
Sham/WT (n=10)	Cage 1	J1	1	15	<i>Object1</i>	15	<i>Object2</i>	12	<i>Familiar</i>	18	<i>Novel</i>	
	Cage 6	J26	1	15		15		23	<i>Novel</i>	7	<i>Familiar</i>	
		old WT-1	1	1	14		16		8	<i>Familiar</i>	22	<i>Novel</i>
			2	2	15		15		20	<i>Novel</i>	10	<i>Familiar</i>
			3	3	15		15		10	<i>Familiar</i>	20	<i>Novel</i>
			4	4	15		15		19	<i>Novel</i>	11	<i>Familiar</i>
	5	no	14		16		11	<i>Familiar</i>	19	<i>Novel</i>		
	old WT-2	6	1	16		14		21	<i>Novel</i>	9	<i>Familiar</i>	
		7	2	15		15		13	<i>Familiar</i>	17	<i>Novel</i>	
		8	no	15		15		21	<i>Novel</i>	9	<i>Familiar</i>	
				Mean	14.90			15.10				
				SEM	0.18			0.18				

Sham/Hv1 KO (n=10)	Hv1-41	6677	1	16		14		13	<i>Familiar</i>	17	<i>Novel</i>
		6678	no	16		14		23	<i>Novel</i>	7	<i>Familiar</i>
	Hv1-42	6679	1	14		16		12	<i>Familiar</i>	18	<i>Novel</i>
		6680	2	15		15		20	<i>Novel</i>	10	<i>Familiar</i>
		6681	no	14		16		12	<i>Familiar</i>	18	<i>Novel</i>
	old Hv1-8	792	no	16		14		18	<i>Novel</i>	12	<i>Familiar</i>
	old Hv1-9	793	no	16		14		11	<i>Familiar</i>	19	<i>Novel</i>
	Hv1-84	1	1	15		15		17	<i>Novel</i>	13	<i>Familiar</i>
		2	2	16		14		12	<i>Familiar</i>	18	<i>Novel</i>
		3	no	16		14		19	<i>Novel</i>	11	<i>Familiar</i>
				Mean	15.40			14.60			
				SEM	0.27			0.27			

TBI/WT (n=8)	Cage 3	J11	1	15		15		13	<i>Familiar</i>	17	<i>Novel</i>	
		J12	2	14		16		16	<i>Novel</i>	14	<i>Familiar</i>	
		J14	4	17		13		15	<i>Familiar</i>	15	<i>Novel</i>	
	Cage 4	J16	1	15		15		17	<i>Novel</i>	13	<i>Familiar</i>	
		J17	2	15		15		14	<i>Familiar</i>	16	<i>Novel</i>	
		J18	3	15		15		17	<i>Novel</i>	13	<i>Familiar</i>	
		bad left eye	J19	4	14		16		16	<i>Familiar</i>	14	<i>Novel</i>
			J20	no	16		14		15	<i>Novel</i>	15	<i>Familiar</i>
				Mean	15.13			14.88				
				SEM	0.35			0.35				

TBI/Hv1 KO (n=7)	Hv1-34	6645	1	15		15		15	<i>Familiar</i>	15	<i>Novel</i>
		6646	2	14		16		18	<i>Novel</i>	12	<i>Familiar</i>
		6648	3	14		16		14	<i>Familiar</i>	16	<i>Novel</i>
		6650	4	15		15		19	<i>Novel</i>	11	<i>Familiar</i>
	Hv1-36	6660	1	14		16		17	<i>Novel</i>	13	<i>Familiar</i>
		6663	2	16		14		14	<i>Familiar</i>	16	<i>Novel</i>
		6666	no	16		14		17	<i>Novel</i>	13	<i>Familiar</i>

8/8/2019 Nest Building Test, Performed by Yun Li (PID 351-352)

Cage#	Groups	Mouse ID	Tail #	Nestlet Weight (pre)	Nestlet Weight (post)	Rating	Amount Shredded	Percentage Shredded	
Sham/WT (n=10)	Cage 1	J1	1	2.4	0	4	2.4	100.00	
		J26	1	2.2	0	4	2.2	100.00	
	old WT-1	1	1	2.5	2.4	1	0.1	4.00	
		2	2	2.7	0.9	2	1.8	66.67	
		3	3	2.5	0	4	2.5	100.00	
		4	4	2.4	0	4	2.4	100.00	
		5	no	2.5	0	3	2.5	100.00	
		6	1	2.5	2.5	1	0	0.00	
		7	2	2.7	0	4	2.7	100.00	
		8	no	2.3	0	5	2.3	100.00	
Mean				2.47	0.58	3.20	1.89	77.07	
SEM				0.05	0.32	0.44	0.32	12.94	
Sham/Hv1 KO (n=10)	Hv1-41	6677	1	2.4	0	4	2.4	100.00	
		6678	no	2.5	0	5	2.5	100.00	
	Hv1-42	6679	1	2.3	0	4	2.3	100.00	
		6680	2	2.4	0	4	2.4	100.00	
	old Hv1-8	6681	no	2.5	0	4	2.5	100.00	
		792	no	2.4	0	5	2.4	100.00	
	old Hv1-9	793	no	2.4	0	5	2.4	100.00	
		Hv1-84	1	1	2.8	0	5	2.8	100.00
		2	2	2.7	0	4	2.7	100.00	
		3	no	2.2	0	4	2.2	100.00	
Mean				2.46	0.00	4.40	2.46	100.00	
SEM				0.06	0.00	0.16	0.06	0.00	
TBI/WT (n=8)	Cage 3	J11	1	2.4	0	3	2.4	100.00	
		J12	2	2.6	0	4	2.6	100.00	
	Cage 4	J14	4	2.5	0	4	2.5	100.00	
		J16	1	2.8	0	4	2.8	100.00	
	J17	2	2.3	0	5	2.3	100.00		
	J18	3	2.4	0.4	3	2	83.33		
	J19	4	2.7	0	4	2.7	100.00		
	J20	no	2.3	0	5	2.3	100.00		
	Mean				2.50	0.05	4.00	2.45	97.92
	SEM				0.07	0.05	0.27	0.09	2.08
TBI/Hv1 KO (n=8)	Hv1-34	6645	1	2.5	0	5	2.5	100.00	
		6646	2	2.4	0	5	2.4	100.00	
	Hv1-36	6648	3	2.4	0	5	2.4	100.00	
		6650	4	2.3	0	5	2.3	100.00	
		6660	1	2.4	0	4	2.4	100.00	
		6663	2	2.3	0	5	2.3	100.00	
	6666	no	2.3	0	5	2.3	100.00		
	Mean				2.37	0.00	4.86	2.37	100.00
SEM				0.03	0.00	0.14	0.03	0.00	

8/1/2020 Success Preference Test Pro, Performed by Van LIPSD 202-3025

Category	Item	Unit	Brand	Weight	Volume	Calories	Protein	Fat	Carbohydrate	Fiber	Sugar	Sodium	Cholesterol	Other
Succinyl-L-Asp	ASPI	g	ASPI	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	ASPI	g	ASPI	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	ASPI	g	ASPI	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	ASPI	g	ASPI	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Succinyl-L-Glu	GLU	g	GLU	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	GLU	g	GLU	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	GLU	g	GLU	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	GLU	g	GLU	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Succinyl-L-Phe	PHI	g	PHI	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	PHI	g	PHI	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	PHI	g	PHI	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	PHI	g	PHI	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Succinyl-L-Tyr	TYR	g	TYR	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	TYR	g	TYR	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	TYR	g	TYR	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	TYR	g	TYR	10.0	10.0	100	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

8/19/2019 Hot Plate, Performed by Yun Li (PID 363)

Cage#	Group	Mouse ID	Trial 1			Trial 2			Average				
			Tail #	Start Temp	Stop Temp	Latency	Start Temp	Stop Temp	Latency	Start Temp	Stop Temp	Latency	
Sham/WT (n=10)													
Cage 6		226	1	30.3	49.2	118.93	30	48.5	121.19	30.15	49.35	119.75	
			1	23.8	47.9	111.15	30.6	46.2	100.8	30.2	47.05	105.975	
old WT-1		1	1	30	49.5	120.93	30	49.5	120.42	30	49.5	120.675	
			2	29.7	48.6	115.47	29.4	49.5	121.88	29.55	49.05	119.175	
			3	3	23.8	48.8	117	29.2	49	117.65	29.5	48.9	117.325
			4	4	29.3	48.7	117.07	29.3	49.3	119.81	29.3	49	118.44
			5	no	29.9	49.4	119.19	29.3	49.2	118.95	29.6	49.3	119.07
old WT-2		6	1	29.6	49.1	116.5	29.7	48.7	116.5	29.65	48.9	116.5	
			7	2	29.2	49.9	123.78	29.3	49.2	116.95	29.25	49.55	120.365
			8	no	29.7	49.3	120.18	29.3	49.3	119.96	29.5	49.8	120.17
			Mean							29.67	48.99	117.75	
			SEM							0.11	0.23	1.37	
Sham/Hv1 KO (n=10)													
Hv1-41		6677	1	29.6	47.6	110.51	29.5	48.2	113.07	29.55	47.9	111.79	
			no	29.4	49.8	116.51	29.5	49.7	122.98	29.45	49.75	119.745	
Hv1-42		6679	1	29.8	47.2	109.56	30	47.6	109.04	29.9	47.4	107.8	
			2	25.5	48.8	117	29.2	49.5	121.37	29.35	49.15	119.185	
			no	29.3	48.7	116.85	29.8	49.3	119.75	29.55	49	118.1	
old Hv1-8		792	no	30.3	47.7	110.92	29.6	46.1	101.14	29.85	46.9	106.03	
old Hv1-9		793	no	29.7	47.9	111.5	29.9	47.3	107.21	29.8	47.6	109.355	
Hv1-84		1	1	29.8	50	123.57	29.7	47.7	111	29.75	48.85	117.285	
			2	2	29.9	45.9	98.93	29.5	45.8	99	29.7	45.85	99.295
			3	no	29.5	48.4	114.4	29.4	48.1	112.45	29.45	48.25	113.425
			Mean							29.64	48.07	112.22	
			SEM							0.06	0.37	2.11	
TBU/WT (n=8)													
Cage 3		111	1	29.6	50	123.61	29.6	50	123.72	29.6	50	123.665	
			2	29.6	50	123.48	29.5	50	123.54	29.55	50	123.51	
			14	4	29.3	48.7	116.75	29.5	48.5	116.37	29.4	48.6	116.56
Cage 4		116	1	30	50	123.11	29.6	50	123.73	29.8	50	123.42	
			17	3	29.4	50	123.69	29.2	49.6	122.7	29.35	49.8	123.195
			18	3	29.3	45.4	114.8	29.3	49.3	115.68	29.3	48.85	117.24
			119	4	29.2	50	123.77	29.3	50	123.53	29.25	50	123.65
			120	no	29.5	49.3	118.76	29.3	48.5	115.81	29.45	48.85	117.285
			Mean							29.46	49.51	121.07	
			SEM							0.06	0.22	1.19	
TBU/Hv1 KO (n=7)													
Hv1-34		6645	1	29.9	48.9	116.77	29.5	49.7	122.75	29.7	49.3	119.76	
			2	29.6	48.3	113.69	29.5	47.8	111.07	29.55	48.05	112.38	
			6648	3	29.8	48.6	116.69	29.6	49	118.11	29.6	48.8	117.4
			6650	4	29.4	49.2	119.23	29.2	48.8	117.28	29.3	49	118.255
Hv1-36		6660	1	29.8	49.4	120.19	30	48.8	117	29.9	49.1	118.595	
			2	29.5	47.1	107.7	29.9	47.2	106.59	29.7	47.25	107.145	
			6666	no	29.7	48.5	115.96	29.4	48.6	116.42	29.55	48.55	115.69
			Mean							29.61	48.58	115.60	
			SEM							0.07	0.27	1.68	

Start Temperature	Sham-WT	Sham-Hv1 KO	TBU-WT	TBU-Hv1 KO
Mean	29.67	29.64	29.46	29.61
SEM	0.11	0.06	0.06	0.07

End Temperature	Sham-WT	Sham-Hv1 KO	TBU-WT	TBU-Hv1 KO
Mean	48.99	48.07	49.51	48.54
SEM	0.23	0.17	0.22	0.27

Latency Time	Sham-WT	Sham-Hv1 KO	TBU-WT	TBU-Hv1 KO
Mean	117.75	112.22	121.07	115.60
SEM	1.37	2.11	1.19	1.68

